

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 19-06-2020

Accepted: 28-07-2020

Published: 19-08-2020

Editor: Dr. Natarajan Gajendran

Citation: Pramanik P, Pramanik P (2020) Pathogenesis and preventive approach of hypercoagulopathy and microvascular thrombosis induced mortality from COVID-19. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 13(30): 3076-3087. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/V13i30.969>

* **Corresponding author.**

puru.pra@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2020 Pramanik & Pramanik. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Pathogenesis and preventive approach of hypercoagulopathy and microvascular thrombosis induced mortality from COVID-19

Parthiba Pramanik¹, Purushottam Pramanik^{2*}

¹ Nil Ratan Sirkar Medical College and Hospital, West Bengal, Kolkatta, India

² Department of Zoology, Durgapur Government College, West Bengal, Durgapur, India

Abstract

Background: COVID-19 is the current pandemic infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS Cov-2). Pulmonary collapse in severe critical COVID-19 patients may be due to development of multiple micro thrombi within pulmonary vasculature. As COVID-19 pandemic is accelerating, it is important to understand the molecular mechanism through which SARS-Cov2 induces hypercoagulopathy and intravascular thrombosis to be able to design more appropriate therapy. Focus of this review is to identify mechanisms through re-analysis of publicly available data by which SARS-Cov2 infection induce mortality by augmenting intravascular thrombosis and attempt to understand therapeutic approach to it. **Findings:** SARS Cov-2 accesses host cells via membrane bound angiotensin converting enzyme-2 (ACE2). This leads to imbalance of renin angiotensin system (RAS) increase ratio of Ag-II: Ag-1-7. Ag-II stimulates release of IP-10 from endothelium which upregulates local renin angiotensin system in endothelial cell by positive feedback process. Therefore it is suggested that angiotensin-II of renin angiotensin systemr in endothelial cells sustained proinflammatory signal and developed microvascular thrombosis. During inflammation both extrinsic and intrinsic coagulation pathways are activated. Fibrinolysis is suppressed by imbalance activity of two system: Ang-II-PAI-1 (plasminogen activator inhibitor-1) and Bradykinin-tPA (tissue plasminogen activator) system. Therapy with low molecular weight heparin (LMWH), which have anticoagulant and anti-inflammatory property, is associated with better prognostic in patients with severe COVID-19. ACE inhibitors decrease production of Ag-II and increases availability of bradykinin and consequence reduces coagulopathy **Conclusion:** Thus it is concluded that SARS-Cov2 infection induces microvascular thrombosis from hyperinflammation, misbalance between Ag-II and Ag-1-7 and imbalance activity of two system: Ang-II-PAI-1 and bradykinin-tPA system. ACE inhibitor and anticoagulant mainly LMWH and UFH may serve potential role in COVID-19 therapy particularly in patients with hypercoagulopathy and microvascular thrombosis.

Keywords: COVID19; angiotensin converting enzyme; renin angiotensin system; fibrinolysis; microvascular thrombosis; ACE inhibitor; heparin

1 Introduction

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is the current pandemic infection caused by RNA virus named severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS Cov-2). The disease was first observed in Wuhan, China in December 2019 and since then spread globally. On 11th March 2020⁽¹⁾ WHO declared corona outbreak as a pandemic. The COVID pandemic is still in progress. More than 200 countries of the world now suffer from COVID-19⁽²⁾. At present more than 8.0 million people are infected and more than 0.43 million people were died in COVID-19 worldwide mainly from viral pneumonia and multi-organ failure⁽³⁾. Primary symptoms include fever, cough and fatigue. There is no potential therapeutic treatment for COVID-19. The complete spectrum of complication from COVID19 is yet to be elucidated fully. The clinical manifestations vary from asymptomatic to severe illness and death. Immune responses in older people are less efficient hence they are more susceptible to COVID-19 infection⁽⁴⁾.

Available literature suggest that COVID-19 is not only a primary pulmonary disease but also associated with thrombosis of small pulmonary vessels⁽⁵⁾. Multiple occlusions and microthrombi in pulmonary vasculature⁽⁶⁾ was noted, in biopsy or autopsy studies in COVID-19 patients. Thus mortality risk of COVID-19 patients is not only due to ARDS but also from thrombosis in pulmonary and other vessels. In non-survivors of COVID-19 Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) was reported from studies in China⁽⁷⁾. The development of DIC is supported by increase D-dimer, and fibrin degradation products in severe COVID-19 patients⁽⁷⁾. Multiple microthrombi within pulmonary vasculature may contribute deterioration in COVID-19 patients from pulmonary collapse and ARDS. With progressive hyper inflammation, and systemic micro-angiopathy may lead to multiple organ dysfunction, cardiomyopathy, acute kidney and liver failure, mesenteric ischemia and neurological insults⁽⁸⁾. In a recent clinical study on coagulation parameters it was suggested that anti-thrombin, prothrombin time and prothrombin time activity were lower in COVID-19 patients compared with healthy control⁽⁹⁾. Therefore effectively suppressing the hypercoagulopathy and microvascular thrombosis is an important way to prevent the deterioration of COVID-19 patients and save their lives. Use of ACE inhibitors may prevent the occurrence of VTE from RAS activation⁽¹⁰⁾. Studies have also suggested that anticoagulants like LMWH (Low Molecular Weight Heparin) is beneficial for patients with severe Covid-19 infection for its anticoagulant as well as anti-inflammatory properties.^(11,12) Administration of LMWH within 1 week of SARS-Cov2 infection is associated with significant reduction in 28 day mortality rate⁽¹³⁾. Chronic treatment with direct oral anticoagulants (DOA) those directly inhibit coagulation factors reduced mortality in COVID-19 patients⁽⁵⁾. However, the role of anticoagulants in COVID-19 patients require further study. Here we review the recent advances in hypercoagulopathy from SARS-Cov2 infection, including inflammation, and therapeutic approaches to inhibit microvascular thrombosis. By sharing knowledge and deepening our understanding of the COVID-19 mediated hypercoagulopathy and microvascular thrombosis we believe that the community can efficiently develop potential therapy to fight against corona pandemic.

2 Discussion

COVID-19 induced hypercoagulopathy, intravascular thrombosis and its preventive approach is explained next.

2.1 Disseminated intravascular coagulation

Coagulation dysfunction is one of the major cause for death in severe COVID-19⁽¹⁴⁾. Most of the COVID-19 patients who died have met the criteria of disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) proposed by the international Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis^(7,15). Thus it is a pathological term that include both coagulation and fibrinolysis in circulating blood which leads to organ failure from disrupted microcirculation⁽¹⁶⁾. It is highly complex pathological process associated with unregulated thrombin explosion leading to release of free thrombin in the circulation that results in widespread microvascular thrombosis. It involves activation of procoagulant and modulation of fibrinolytic system to induce intravascular coagulation or hemorrhage or both depending on degree of involvement of these systems. Microvascular thrombosis is a type of DIC. COVID-19-induced hyper inflammation and RAS imbalance may contribute to development of intravascular coagulopathy and thrombosis.

Although COVID-19 patients are not typical DIC seen in septicemia in spite of coagulative abnormalities⁽¹⁷⁾. In DIC thrombocytopenia is a key finding along with elevated clotting time. But in COVID-19 confirmed patients platelet count did not change. Thus in COVID-19 patients there is local thrombosis rather than disseminated thrombin generation⁽¹⁷⁾. A recent study reported venous thromboembolism (VTE) in ICU patients with proven COVID-19 pneumonia⁽¹⁸⁾.

2.2 COVID-19 and hyperinflammation

Innate immunity provides the first line of defense against viral infection. Hence, dysregulated and excessive immune response may cause immune damage⁽¹⁹⁾. SARS-Cov-2 enters into type-2 alveolar epithelial cells using membrane bound ACE2 as receptor. After entering into cell cytoplasm it replicate and releases new viral particles. Tissue macrophage (APC) represent the virus particle With MHC1 to cytotoxic T cells. The immune effector cells release cytokines (IL-1beta, IL-2, IL-6, TNF-alfa etc.) and chemokines (CC motif chemokine ligand: CCL-2, CCL-3, CCL-5)^(20,21). Chemokines attract phagocytic cells (monocyte and neutrophil) into infected area. The elevated level of serum cytokines and chemokines are observed in mild to moderate COVID-19 patients⁽²²⁾.

The pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) were expressed by innate immune cells. Such receptors are recognized by cytoplasmic PRR like TLR3 and TLR7⁽²³⁾. SARS-COV inhibits production of IFN-1 through inhibition of TLR3 and TLR7 signaling pathway. The antiviral interferon, INF-1 (INF-alfa and INF-beta), is the key molecule of natural immune response against viral infection. Delays release of IFN-1

in the early stage of SARS-Cov-2 infection sequesters body’s antiviral response⁽¹²⁾ and allowing rapid replication of virus and virus-induced direct pathogenic effects in early stage of the disease^(24,25). The subsequent delayed and persistent IFN-1 response along with cytokines, chemokines and DAMPs enhance monocyte and neutrophils infiltration into lung parenchyma⁽²⁶⁾. Infiltrated monocytes produce high levels of cytokines and chemokines which positively amplify recruitment of innate immune cells to induce hyperinflammation and cytokine storm. Cytokine storm is characteristic feature of severe cases of COVID-19^(27,28).

Death from COVID-19 is more in male than female⁽²⁹⁾. TLR7 genes are located in X-chromosomes. In female there are two X chromosome. Thus one X-chromosome is escaped from viral-induced inactivation and causes more expression of TLR7 in females⁽³⁰⁾. TLR7 agonist induces more IFN-1 release in females⁽³¹⁾ beside this estradiol enhances IFN-1 release following TLR7 agonism⁽³²⁾.

Hence bi-allelic TLR7 expression and estradiol signaling make females less prone to IFN-1 antagonism which lead to more IFN-1 release in early stage of the infection. Thus virus-induce cytokines storm may be due to IFN-1 antagonism (Figure 1).

SARS-Cov infection is associated with T-cell (both CD4+ and CD8+) lymphopenia⁽³³⁾ from direct cytopathic effect of virus and/or T-cell apoptosis from dysregulated cytokine release⁽³⁴⁾. Decrease in T cell numbers are strongly correlated with severity of acute respiratory syndrome⁽³⁵⁾. Normally CD4+ T-cell modulate immune response and suppress hyper inflammation through down regulation inflammatory process^(36,37). Beside this CD4+ lymphopenia impairs adaptive antiviral response through inadequate help to CD8+ T cells and B-cells⁽³⁸⁾.

Fig 1. Mechanism of COVID-19-induced hyperinflammation and its consequences in COVID-19 victim (Abbreviations Ang-II: angiotensin-II; ACE2:angiotensin converting enzyme-2; IL: interleukin, TNF-alfa: tumor necrosisfactor-alfa; IFN: interferon; DAMP: damage associated molecular pattern; PAMP:pathogen associated molecular pattern)

2.3 COVID-19 and renin angiotensin system

SARS-Cov2 interact with membrane bound angiotensin converting enzyme-2 (ACE2) of target cells by their spike glycoproteins⁽³⁹⁾ and then enter into target cell by endocytosis⁽⁴⁰⁾. Binding of spike protein with ACE2 can not be altered by the addition of a specific ACE2 inhibitor suggesting the inability of such receptor to block SARS infection⁽⁴¹⁾. Deficiency of ACE2 is associated with increased vascular permeability,

fluid accumulation in extra alveolar spaces and increased oxidative⁽⁴²⁾.

Renin angiotensin system (RAS) is a cascade of vasoactive peptides involve in the maintenance of cardiovascular homeostasis. This system consists of two principal enzymes: Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) and Angiotensin Converting enzyme-2 (ACE2). ACE cleaves angiotensin-I to angiotensin-II. ACE 2 is captopril insensitive carboxypeptidase⁽⁴³⁾, which cleaves carboxyl terminal peptide bond of angiotensin-I and angiotensin-II and produces Ag-(1-9) and Ag-(1-7) respectively. Catalytic efficiency of ACE2 against Ag-II is remarkably higher than Ag-I⁽⁴⁴⁾. Thus, ACE2 is the main enzyme for Ag-(1-7) generation in many tissues. The elevated ACE activity is associated with reduced ACE2, increase Ag-II formation and increase Ag-(1-7) catabolism, while in reverse condition there is vasodilation from increase ACE2, decrease ACE, decrease Ag-II and increase Ag-(1-7). Ag-II induces lung inflammation, ROS formation, vasoconstriction, proliferation and thrombosis via angiotensin type1 receptor. Ag-(1-7) via mas receptor prevents lung inflammation, induces vasodilation and activates antioxidant system (Figure 2).

Fig 2. Principal components of renin angiotensin system and their roles (Abbreviations Ag-I: angiotensin-I; Ag-II: angiotensin-II; ACE:angiotensin converting enzyme; ACE2: angiotensin converting enzyme-2; PI3-K:Phosphotidyl inositol 3 kinase; NOS: Nitric oxide synthase; SOD: superoxidedismutase; AVP: arginine vaso pressin; AT1: angiotensin type-1)

Number of membrane bound ACE2 decreases as SARS-Cov-2 induces internalization of ACE2. At the same time proinflammatory cytokine, TNF-alfa activates ADAM-17. ADAM17, a membrane bound metallopeptidase, remains in close associated with RAS. ACE2 can be shed from the cell surface through proteolytic cleavage of its external domain by ADAM17⁽⁴⁵⁾.

Neutrophil infiltration into lungs in response to bacterial endotoxin is enhanced from ACE2 deficiency⁽⁴⁶⁾. Liu et al. suggested that plasma Ag-II level was elevated in COVID-19 patients in correlation with viral load⁽⁴⁷⁾. COVID-19-induced lung injury is minimized by Restoration of ACE2 through the administration of recombinant ACE2^(48,49). Children are less susceptible to COVID-19 than adults due to high ACE2 expression⁽⁵⁰⁾.

2.4 Microvascular thrombosis

Microvascular thrombosis is due to enhance intravascular coagulation, suppression of fibrinolysis and inactivation of intravascular anticoagulant. macrophages, neutrophils, the complement system, platelets and coagulation factors to form a clots to prevent spread of pathogens^(51,52). This type of coagulation is called immunothrombosis or thromboinflammation. Uncontrolled and widespread thromboinflammation increases severity of COVID-19. The persistant inflammatory status in severe and critical COVID-19 patient's act as

an important trigger for the coagulation cascade⁽⁵³⁾. Proinflammatory cytokines like IL-1beta, IL-6 and TNF-alfa upregulate pro-coagulants in patients with COVID-19⁽⁵⁴⁾. A cross talk between coagulative haemostasis and inflammation as well as the activation of coagulation cascade during viral infections are well established⁽⁵⁵⁾. During inflammation both extrinsic and intrinsic coagulation pathways are activated. Inflamed endothelial cells and macrophages release tissue factor to initiate activation of extrinsic coagulation system⁽⁵²⁾. PMNs release neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) which activate coagulation factor XII to initiate activation of intrinsic coagulation reaction and inactivates endogenous anticoagulant⁽⁵⁶⁾. Platelets activation is associated with release of P-selectin from stored granules which facilitates the interaction between platelet and neutrophil. Such interaction promotes release of NETs from recruited neutrophil. This intern activates platelet and promotes coagulation by positive feedback system⁽⁵⁷⁾. IL-1 and IL-6 damages vascular endothelium and enhances thrombosis along with tissue factor⁽⁵⁸⁾. Colafrancesco et al (2020) suggested a bidirectional relationship between IL-1 mediated inflammation and coagulation⁽⁵⁹⁾. IL-1beta upregulates the expression of tissue factor which leads to generation of intravascular thrombi⁽⁶⁰⁾. Vascular endothelium releases selectin and endothelin in response to thrombin. The released selectin induces more cytokine release from granulocytes and macrophages⁽⁶¹⁾. The endothelin induces vasoconstriction and vasospasm to augment thrombosis⁽⁶²⁾. Endothelin-1 which is linked to Ag-II via AT1 receptor⁽⁶³⁾, can also activate coagulation cascade and induced microvascular thrombosis⁽⁶⁴⁾ (Figure 3).

Fig 3. Role of SARS-Cov2 infection on augmentation of intravascular coagulation. (Numerical figures indicates number of coagulation factors, ‘a’ represent active factor, NETs indicates neutrophil extracellular traps)

In DIC complement is activated by TNF^(65,66). Complement induced platelets lysis provides more procoagulant to augment the coagulation process. C3a and C5a exert proinflammatory effect⁽⁶⁷⁾ and enhance coagulation process by increasing expression of tissue factor and von Willibrand factor⁽⁶⁸⁾.

The RAS is intrinsically linked to the coagulation cascade and may exacerbate microvascular thrombosis by suppressing fibrinolysis. Ang-II-PAI-1 and Bradykinin-tPA system maintain the rate of fibrinolysis. Ag-II induces PAI-1 expression by endothelial cells via AT1 receptor and develops PAI-1/tPA imbalance (increase ratio of PAI-1/tPA) to hampers fibrinolysis⁽⁶⁹⁾. This leads to fibrin deposition in the alveoli in COVID-19 victims⁽⁷⁰⁾. Ag-II also enhances release of PAI-1 from adipocytes⁽⁷¹⁾. This is an account for increased severity in obese corona victims.

Bradykinin acts on endothelial cells to increase release of plasminogen activator (tPA)⁽⁷²⁾. Elevated Ag-II increase production of aldosterone which enhances activity of ACE. There are two different catalytic domains of ACE, one cleaving Ag-I to Ag-II and other converts bradykinin to inactive peptide. Thus COVID-19-induce increase Ag-II-aldosterone blunts bradykinin mediated increase of tPA. Therefore in COVID-19 patients there is decreased tPA to PAI-1 ratio and promotes hypofibrinolysis. Hyper aldosteronism in COVID-19 is supported by hypokalemia in COVID-19 victims⁽⁷³⁾. It has been shown that aldosterone directly increases PAI-1 expression⁽⁷⁴⁾. Aldosterone levels have been shown to correlate with PAI-1 levels⁽⁷⁵⁾. ACE inhibitors have been shown to reduces PAI-1 levels and increase release of tPA via elevated bradykinin^(76,77). Spironolactone, an aldosterone receptor blocker has been shown to decrease PAI-1 levels⁽⁷⁸⁾ (Figure 4).

Fig 4. ACE-Ag-II and ACE-bradykinin system for the maintenance of endothelial homeostasis (Abbreviations Ang-I: angiotensin-I; Ang-II: angiotensin-II; ACE: angiotensin converting enzyme; NO: Nitric oxide; tPA: tissue plasminogen activator; PAI-1: plasminogen activator inhibitor-1)

Renin- angiotensin system and bradykinin-nitric oxide system have major role in endothelial homeostasis. Bradykinin via bradykinin receptor-2 (B2R) induces the release of nitric oxide, prostacyclin and endothelium-derived- hyperpolarizing-factor (EDHF) and tissue plasminogen activator from endothelium. Thus it induces vasodilation with increasing formation of NO and prostacyclin and hyperpolarization of membrane via EDHF^(79,80). In endothelial cell bradykinin via bradykinin receptor-2 (B2R) induces the release of nitric oxide, prostacyclin and endothelium-derived- hyperpolarizing-factor (EDHF) and tissue plasminogen activator. Bradykinin induces vasodilation with increasing formation of NO and prostacyclin and hyperpolarization of membrane via EDHF^(79,80). NO from endothelium diffuses to surrounding tissues and perform various cardioprotective effects include smooth muscle relaxation, prevention of leukocytes and platelet adhesion into vascular wall⁽⁸¹⁾.

Ag-II -induces ROS which is responsible for NO breakdown and reduced eNOS derived NO⁽⁸²⁾. It induces oxidative stress to increases expression of PTI-1 and thereby favoring thrombosis⁽⁸³⁾. Ag-II also increase release of cytokines to increase adhesiveness of endothelium to inflammatory cells and consequently induces inflammation and thrombosis⁽⁸⁴⁾.

Fig 5. Molecular mechanism of suppression of fibrinolysis in COVID-19 victims (Abbreviations Ag-II: angiotensin-II; ACE2:angiotensin converting enzyme2; tPA: tissue plasminogen activator; PAI-1:plasminogen activator inhibitor-1)

Ag-II activates nuclear factor kB (NF-kB) in monocytes, macrophages and endothelial cells which induces production of chemokines like monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), IL-6, and IL-8^(85,86). Release chemokines recruit monocytes and neutrophils at the infective tissue to induce cytokines storm.

Ag-II stimulates release of CXC chemokines, IP-10 from endothelium⁽⁸⁷⁾ and augments apoptosis and cell senescence of endothelial cell⁽⁸⁸⁾. Neutralization of IP-10 inhibits Ag-II-induced apoptosis. It is now established that IP-10 upregulates local renin angiotensin system in endothelial cell by positive feedback process. Therefore it is suggested that angiotensin-II renin angiotensin system circuit in endothelial cells sustained proinflammatory signal and microvascular thrombosis (Figure 6).

Fig 6. Endothelial positive feedback on renin-angiotensin system for over formation of Ag-II and augmentation of microvascular thrombosis COVID-19 victim (Abbreviations ACE: angiotensin converting enzyme; ACE2: angiotensin converting enzyme 2; IL: Interleukin; MCP: monocyte chemoattractant protein)

2.5 Theoretical treatment strategy

Vascular health depends on functional integrity of endothelium. SARS-Cov2 infection is associated with Ag-II-induced oxidative stress. Such stressful environment develops pro-inflammatory and thrombotic state. NO, endothelial derived factor, maintain endothelial function. Thus endothelial dysfunction is associated with decreased bioavailability of NO⁽⁸⁹⁾ either from reduced production or increased breakdown⁽⁹⁰⁾. From endothelium NO diffuses to surrounding tissues and perform cardio-protective action include relaxation of smooth muscle cells, prevention of leukocyte adhesion to vascular wall, prevention of platelet adhesion and aggregation and proliferation of smooth muscle cell^(81,90).

Endothelial cell activation is a unique mechanism of COVID-19 mediated microvascular injury, thrombosis and multi organ failure⁽⁹¹⁾ which is aggravated by hypoxia⁽⁹²⁾. Pulmonary embolism with occlusion and micro thrombosis in pulmonary small vessels is observed in critical COVID-19 patients⁽⁹³⁾. Beside pulmonary embolism, COVID-19 can cause a sepsis associated DIC⁽⁹⁴⁾. Thus there is an increasing interest in the treatment of COVID-19 using agents that ameliorate endothelial dysfunctions and hypo-fibrinolysis and prevent intravascular coagulation.

Ag-II is the main culprit in COVID-induced endothelial dysfunction⁽⁹⁵⁾. Elevated Ag-II Stimulates ROS generation which causes breakdown of NO⁽⁷³⁾. Besides this ROS also inhibits eNOS by inducing uncoupling to decrease NO production⁽⁸²⁾. Oxidative stress increases expression of Plasminogen activator Inhibitor-1 (PAI-1) to enhance thrombosis⁽⁸³⁾. The adhesiveness of endothelial cell surface to inflammatory cells is enhanced by ROS. Thus oxidative stress condition promotes inflammation and thrombosis^(96,97).

Ag-II-induced endothelial dysfunction is augmented in absence of counter-actor, bradykinin. Bradykinin via bradykinin receptor-2 (abundantly expressed in endothelium) causes release of NO and prostacyclin to induce vasodilation⁽⁹⁸⁾. Bradykinin has antithrombotic property by increasing tissue type plasminogen activator⁽⁹⁹⁾. In COVID-19 victims there is degradation of bradykinin via Ag-II mediated hyperaldosteronism. The increase level of Ag-II and aldosterone in COVID-19 infection may be associated with hypofibrinolysis leading to

a decrease tPA to PAI-1 ratio. This leads to poor resolution of alveolar lesions and fibrosis in COVID-19 patients⁽¹⁰⁰⁾. High level of Ag-II may exacerbate endothelial dysfunction and enhance lung injury. ACE inhibitors have been shown to improve endothelial function⁽⁸⁾. It also increase NO production by two ways: inhibiting production of Ag-II (which decrease NO production by inhibiting eNOS and enhances NO breakdown) and inhibiting the breakdown of bradykinin (which stimulate local release of NO). Beside this ACE inhibitor increases availability of bradykinin to enhance fibrinolysis and consequence reduces coagulopathy of endothelium. There are two different catalytic domains of ACE, one cleaves Ag-I and other degrades bradykinin. ACE inhibitor have a greater affinity for the bradykinin than for Ag-I. Thus such inhibitor decreases bradykinin degradation⁽¹⁰¹⁾. Thus ACE inhibitor can be considered as pharmacological therapeutic agent to prevent COVID-19 associated microvascular thrombosis. The combined effects of ACE inhibitor on both the pulmonary system and haemostasis may be a tentative target in COVID-19.

A previous study indicated that anticoagulation treatment using LMWH reduced mortality in severe COVID-19 patients with coagulopathy⁽¹¹⁾. Anticoagulation treatment was recommended in patients in the viremia and acute clinical phases of COVID-19 induced pathogenesis⁽¹⁰²⁾. SARS-Cov-induced inflammation may lead to excessive activation of coagulation in these phases⁽¹⁰³⁾. Anticoagulation therapy with unfractionated heparin (UFH) caused successfully recovered from moderate to severe COVID-19 cases in Japan⁽¹⁰⁴⁾. In addition to anticoagulant property heparin has anti-inflammatory and direct antiviral⁽¹⁰⁵⁾. Heparin inhibits neutrophil activation to minimize formation of cytokines and reduces activation of endothelium after binding with cytokines⁽¹⁰⁶⁾. It was reported that heparin directly occupies spike protein to prevent SARS-Cov-ACE2 interaction, and thereby blocks entry of virus into host cell⁽¹⁰⁷⁾. It also down regulates IL-6⁽¹⁰⁸⁾, which is elevated in COVID-19 patients⁽¹⁰⁹⁾. Heparin binds and forms a complex with plasma antithrombin III, activating it. This produces a conformational change in antithrombin which accelerates its binding to clotting factors Xa, IIa, IXa, XIIa and XIIIa resulting in inhibition of the factors. In this way Heparin works as an anticoagulant which can be used to treat Covid-19 patients. Prophylactic LMWH is recommended by WHO against venous thromboembolism in critically ill COVID-19 patients⁽¹¹⁰⁾

3 Summary and Conclusion

The hall mark of SARS-COV2 infection is hyperinflammation which promotes thrombosis through activation of endothelium, platelets, and coagulation factors, and inhibition of fibrinolysis. COVID-19 associated coagulopathy is accompanied by high mortality rate from thrombotic complications. Ag-II is the main culprit in COVID-induced endothelial dysfunction. SARS-Cov2 infection is associated with misbalance between Ag-II and Ag-I-7 (increase ratio of Ag-II: Ag-I-7) which leads to hyperinflammation. Imbalance activity of two system: Ang-II-PAI-1 and bradykinin-tPA system (with increased activity of Ag-II-PAI-1) suppress fibrinolysis. ACE inhibitor which decreases the formation of Ag-II as well as prevents degradation of bradykinin may serve potential role against microvascular thrombosis from COVID-19. On the other hand LMWH may be considered as potent therapeutic agent not only due to its antithrombotic property but also from anti-inflammatory and anti-viral activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge Mr. Sudeep Kumar Das, Assistant Professor in Physics, Durgapur Government College, for his support in preparation of figure. Authors acknowledge the immense help received from the scholars whose articles are cited and included in references in this review article.

Funding: No funding sources

Conflict Interest: None declared

Ethical approval: Not required

References

- 1) WHO. WHO Director General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19. 2020. Available from: <https://www.who.int/dg/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19>.
- 2) Corona virus Update . 2020. Available from: <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus>
- 3) Hui SD, Azhar IE, Madani AT, Ntoumi F, Kock R, Dar O, et al. The continuing 2019-nCoV epidemic threat of novel coronaviruses to global health — The latest 2019 novel coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2020;91:264–266. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.01.009>.
- 4) Nikolich-Zugich J, Knox KS, Rios CT, Natt B, Bhattacharya D, Fain MJ. SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 in older adults: what we may expect regarding pathogenesis, immune responses, and outcomes. *GeroScience*. 2020;42(2):505–514. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11357-020-00186-0>.
- 5) Rossi R, Coppi F, Talarico M, Boriani G. Protective role of chronic treatment with direct oral anticoagulants in elderly patients affected by interstitial pneumonia in COVID-19 era. *European Journal of Internal Medicine*. 2020;77:158–160. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejim.2020.06.006>.
- 6) Luo W, Yu H, Gou J, Li X, Sun Y, Li J, et al. Clinical pathology of critical patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19). 2020. Available from: <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202002.0407/v1>.
- 7) Tang N, Li D, Wang X, Sun Z. Abnormal coagulation parameters are associated with poor prognosis in patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2020.
- 8) Henry BM, Vikse J, Benoit S, Favaloro EJ, Lippi G. Hyperinflammation and derangement of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system in COVID-19: A novel hypothesis for clinically suspected hypercoagulopathy and microvascular immunothrombosis. *Clinica Chimica Acta*. 2020;507:167–173. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2020.04.027>.
- 9) Han H, Yang L, Liu R, et al. Prominent changes in blood coagulation of patients with SARS-Cov-2 infection. *Clin Chem Lab Med*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1515/ccim-2020-0188>.
- 10) Chae YK, Khemasuwan D, Dimou A, Neagu S, Chebrolo L, Gupta S, et al. Inhibition of Renin Angiotensin Axis May Be Associated with Reduced Risk of Developing Venous Thromboembolism in Patients with Atherosclerotic Disease. *PLoS ONE*. 2014;9(1):e87813–e87813. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0087813>.

- 11) Tang N, Bai H, Chen X, Gong J, Li D, Sun Z. Anticoagulant treatment is associated with decreased mortality in severe coronavirus disease 2019 patients with coagulopathy. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 2020;18(5):1094–1099. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/jth.14817>.
- 12) Shi C, Wang C, Wang H, Yang C, Cai F, Zeng F. Clinical observations of low molecular weight heparin in relieving inflammation in COVID-19 patients: A retrospective cohort study. *Medrxiv*. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.28.20046144>.
- 13) Marietta M, Coluccio V, Luppi M. Covid-19, coagulopathy and venous thrombosis: more questions than answers. *Int J Emergency Med*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-020-02432-x>.
- 14) Wu C, Chen X, Cai Y, Xia J, Zhou X, Xu S. Risk factors associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome and death in patients with coronavirus disease 2019 pneumonia in Wuhan, China. *JAMA Intern Med*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.0994>.
- 15) Tang N, Li D, Wang X, Sun Z. Abnormal coagulation parameters are associated with poor prognosis in patients with novel corona virus pneumonia. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jth.14768>.
- 16) Toh CH. Disseminated intravascular coagulation: old disease, new hope. *BMJ*. 2003;327(7421):974–977. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.327.7421.974>.
- 17) Atallah B, Mallah SI, AlMahmeed W. Anticoagulation in COVID-19. *European Heart Journal - Cardiovascular Pharmacotherapy*. 2020;6(4):260–261. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/ehjcvp/pvaa036>.
- 18) Klok FA, Kruip MJ, Meer NJVD, Arbous MS, Gommers DA, Kant KM, et al. Incidence of thrombotic complications in critically ill ICU patients with COVID-19. *Thromb Res*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2020.04.013>.
- 19) Davidson S, Maini MK, Wack A. Disease-Promoting Effects of Type I Interferons in Viral, Bacterial, and Coinfections. *Journal of Interferon & Cytokine Research*. 2015;35(4):252–264. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1089/jir.2014.0227>.
- 20) Law KWH, Cheung CY, Ng HY, Sia SF, Chan YO, Luk W, et al. Chemokine up-regulation in SARS-coronavirus-infected, monocyte-derived human dendritic cells. *Blood*. 2005;106(7):2366–2374. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1182/blood-2004-10-4166>.
- 21) Lau KPS, Lau CYC, Chan KH, Li PYC, Chen H, Jin DY, et al. Delayed induction of proinflammatory cytokines and suppression of innate antiviral response by the novel Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus: implications for pathogenesis and treatment. *Journal of General Virology*. 2013;94(12):2679–2690. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1099/vir.0.055533-0>.
- 22) Zhou G, Chen S, Chen Z. Advances in COVID-19: the virus, the pathogen and evidence based control and therapeutic strategies. *Front Med*. 2020;14(2):117–125.
- 23) Messina F, Giombini E, Agrati C, Vairo F, Bartoli TA, Almoghazi S. COVID-19: viral-host interactome analyzed by network based-approach model to study pathogenesis of SARS Cov-2 infection. *BMCJ Translational Medicine*. 2020;18:233–242.
- 24) Chen X, Yang X, Zheng Y, Yang Y, Sing Y, Chen Z. SARS coronavirus papine-like protease inhibits the type-1 interferon signaling pathway through interaction with the STING-TRAF3-TBK1 complex. *Protein Cell*. 2014;5:369–381.
- 25) Mirzaei R, Karampoor S, Sholeh M, Moradi P, Ranjbar R, Ghasemi F. A contemporary review on pathogenesis and immunity of COVID-19 infection. *Molecular Biology Reports*. 2020;47(7):5365–5376. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11033-020-05621-1>.
- 26) Channappanavar R, Fehr AR, Vijay R, Mack M, Zhao J, Meyerholz DK, et al. Dysregulated Type I Interferon and Inflammatory Monocyte-Macrophage Responses Cause Lethal Pneumonia in SARS-CoV-Infected Mice. *Cell Host & Microbe*. 2016;19(2):181–193. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2016.01.007>.
- 27) Mehta P, McAuley DE, Brown M, Sanchez E, Tattersall RS, Manson JJ. COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression. *The Lancet*. 2020;395(10229):1033–1034. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30628-0](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30628-0).
- 28) Soy M, Keser G, Atagündüz P, Tabak F, Atagündüz I, Kayhan S. Cytokine storm in COVID-19: pathogenesis and overview of anti-inflammatory agents used in treatment. *Clinical Rheumatology*. 2020;39(7):2085–2094. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10067-020-05190-5>.
- 29) Wenham C, Smith J, Morgan R. COVID-19: the gendered impacts of the outbreak. *The Lancet*. 2020;395(10227):846–848. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30526-2](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30526-2).
- 30) Souyris M, Cenac C, Azar P, Daviaud D, Canivet A, Grunenwald S, et al. TLR7 escapes X chromosome inactivation in immune cells. *Science Immunology*. 2018;3(19):eaap8855–eaap8855. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1126/sciimmunol.aap8855>.
- 31) Berghofer B, Formmer T, Haley G. TLR7 ligands induce higher IFN- α production in females. *Journal of Immunology*. 2006;177:2088–2096.
- 32) Seillet C, Laffont S, Trémollières F, Rouquié N, Ribot C, Arnal JE, et al. The TLR-mediated response of plasmacytoid dendritic cells is positively regulated by estradiol in vivo through cell-intrinsic estrogen receptor α signaling. *Blood*. 2012;119(2):454–464. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1182/blood-2011-08-371831>.
- 33) Li T, Qiu Z, Zhang L, Han Y, He W, Liu Z, et al. Significant changes of peripheral T-lymphocyte subsets in patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome. *Journal of Infective Diseases*. 2004;189(4):648–651.
- 34) Wang X, Xu W, Hu G, Xia S, Sun Z, Liu Z, et al. Cov-2 infects T-lymphocytes through its spike protein mediated membrane fusion. *Cellulau and molecular Immunology*. 2020;5:1–3. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41423-020-0424-9>.
- 35) Li T, Qui Z, Han Y, Wang Z, Fan H, Lu W, et al. Rapid loss of both CD4+ and CD8+ T lymphocyte subsets during the acute phase of severe acute respiratory syndrome. *Chinese Medical Journal*. 2003;116(7):985–987.
- 36) Chen J, Lau YF, Lamirande WE, Paddock CD, Bartlett JH, Zaki RS, et al. Cellular Immune Responses to Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (SARS-CoV) Infection in Senescent BALB/c Mice: CD4+ T Cells Are Important in Control of SARS-CoV Infection. *Journal of Virology*. 2010;84(3):1289–1301. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1128/jvi.01281-09>.
- 37) Channappanavar R, Perlman S. Pathogenic human coronavirus infections: causes and consequences of cytokine storm and immunopathology. *Seminars in Immunopathology*. 2017;39(5):529–539. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00281-017-0629-x>.
- 38) Daley-Bauer PL, Wynn MG, Mocarski SE. Cytomegalovirus Impairs Antiviral CD8+ T Cell Immunity by Recruiting Inflammatory Monocytes. *Immunity*. 2012;37(1):122–133. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.immuni.2012.04.014>.
- 39) Perrotta F, Matera MG, Cazzola M, Bianco A. Severe respiratory SARS-CoV2 infection: Does ACE2 receptor matter? *Respiratory Medicine*. 2020;168. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rmed.2020.105996>.
- 40) Vaduganathan M, Vardeny O, Michel T, McMurray J, Pfeffer AM, Solomon DS. Renin–Angiotensin–Aldosterone System Inhibitors in Patients with Covid-19. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2020;382(17):1653–1659. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1056/nejmsr2005760>.
- 41) Li F. Receptor recognition and cross-species infections of SRS corona virus. *Antivir Res*. 2013;100:246–254.
- 42) Fyhrquist F, Saijonmaa O. Renin-angiotensin system revisited. *Journal of Internal Medicine*. 2008;264(3):224–236. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2796.2008.01981.x>.
- 43) Tipnis SR, Hooper MM, Hyde R, Karran E, Christie G, Turner AJ. A human homolog of angiotensin-converting-enzyme. Cloning and functional expression as a captopril-insensitive carboxypeptidase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2000;275:33238–33281.
- 44) Rice IG, Thomas AD, Grant JP, Turner JA, Hooper MN. Evaluation of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE), its homologue ACE2 and neprilysin in angiotensin peptide metabolism. *Biochemical Journal*. 2004;383(1):45–51. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1042/bj20040634>.
- 45) Lambert DW, Yarski M, Warner FJ, Thornhill P, Parkin ET, Smith AI, et al. Tumor necrosis factor- α convertase (ADAM17) mediates regulated ectodomain shedding of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-Cov) receptor, angiotensin converting enzyme2. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2005;280:30113–30119.
- 46) Sodhi PC, Wohlford-Lenane C, Yamaguchi Y, Prindle T, Fulton WB, Wang S, et al. Attenuation of pulmonary ACE2 activity impairs inactivation of des-Arg9 bradykinin/BKB1R axis and facilitates LPS-induced neutrophil infiltration. *American Journal of Physiology-Lung Cellular and Molecular Physiology*. 2018;314(1):L17–L31. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1152/ajplung.00498.2016>.
- 47) Liu Y, Yang Y, Zhang C, Huang F, Wang F, Yuan J, et al. Clinical and biochemical indexes from 2019-nCov infected patients linked to viral loads and lung injury. *Science China Lifescience*. 2020;63:364–374.
- 48) Zou Z, Yan Y, Shu Y, Gao R, Sun Y, Li X, et al. Angiotensin Converting enzyme-2 protect from lethal avian influenza: A H5N1 infection. *Natural Communication*. 2014;5:3594–3594.
- 49) Gu H, Xie Z, Li T, Zhang S, Lai C, Zhu P, et al. Angiotensin converting enzyme-2 inhibits lung injury induced by respiratory syncytial virus. *Scientific Report*. 2016;6.
- 50) Dhochak N, Singhal T, Kabra SK, Lodha R. Pathophysiology of COVID-19: Why Children Fare Better than Adults? *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020;87(7):537–546. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12098-020-03322-y>.
- 51) Gaertner F, Massberg S. Blood coagulation in immunothrombosis—At the frontline of intravascular immunity. *Seminars in Immunology*. 2016;28(6):561–569. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.smim.2016.10.010>.

- 52) Jackson PS, Darbousset R, Schoenwaelder MS. Thromboinflammation: challenges of therapeutically targeting coagulation and other host defense mechanisms. *Blood*. 2019;133(9):906–918. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1182/blood-2018-11-882993>.
- 53) Cao W, Li T. COVID-19: towards understanding of pathogenesis. *Cell Res*. 2020;30:367–369.
- 54) Henry BM, Delivera M, Benoit S, Plebani M, Lippi G. Hematologic, biochemical and immune biomarkers abnormalities associated with severe illness and mortality in coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a meta-analysis. *Clin Chem Lab Med*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1515/cclm-2020-0369>.
- 55) Boccia M, Aronne L, Celia B, Mazzeo G, Ceparano M, D'Agano V, et al. COVID-19 and coagulative axis: review of emerging aspects in a novel disease. *Monaldi Archives for Chest Disease*. 2020;90(2). Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4081/monaldi.2020.1300>.
- 56) Keragala CB, Draxler DF, McQuiltan ZK. Haemostasis and innate immunity: a review of the intricate relationship between coagulation and complement pathway. *British Journal of Haematology*. 2018;180:782–798.
- 57) Zucoloto AZ, Jenne CN. Platelet-neutrophil interplay insights into neutrophil extracellular traps-driven coagulation in infection. *Front Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2019. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcvm.2019.00085>.
- 58) Elsayed Y, Nakagawa K, Ichikawa K. Expression of tissue factor and interleukin I beta in a novel rabbit model of disseminated intravascular coagulation induced by carrageenan and lipopolysaccharide. *Pathobiology*. 1995;63:328–340.
- 59) Colafrancesco S, Scrivero R, Barbatì C, Conti F, Priori R. Targeting the Immune System for Pulmonary Inflammation and Cardiovascular Complications in COVID-19 Patients. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2020;11. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.01439>.
- 60) Elsayed YA, Nakagawa K, Ichikawa K, Ohkawara S, Sueishi K. Expression of Tissue Factor and Interleukin-1 β ; in a Novel Rabbit Model of Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation Induced by Carrageenan and Lipopolysaccharide. *Pathobiology*. 1995;63(6):328–340. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000163969>.
- 61) Okajima K, Uchiba M, Murakami K, Okabe H, Takatsuki K. Plasma levels of soluble E-selectin in patients with disseminated intravascular coagulation. *American Journal of Hematology*. 1997;54(3):219–224. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1096-8652\(199703\)54:3<219::aid-ajh8>3.0.co;2-z](https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1096-8652(199703)54:3<219::aid-ajh8>3.0.co;2-z).
- 62) Ishibashi M, Ito N, Fujita M, Furue H, Yamaji T. Endothelin-1 as an aggravating factor of disseminated intravascular coagulation associated with malignant neoplasms. *Cancer*. 1994;73(1):191–195. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142\(19940101\)73:1<191::aid-cnrcr2820730133>3.0.co;2-x](https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142(19940101)73:1<191::aid-cnrcr2820730133>3.0.co;2-x).
- 63) Chua BHL, Chua CC, Diglio CA, Siu BB. Regulation of endothelin-1 mRNA by angiotensin II in rat heart endothelial cells. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular Cell Research*. 1993;1178(2):201–206. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0167-4889\(93\)90010-m](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0167-4889(93)90010-m).
- 64) Halim A, Kanayama N, Maradny EE, Maehara K, Masahiko H, Terao T. Endothelin-1 increased immunoreactive von Willebrand factor in endothelial cells and induced micro thrombosis in rats. *Thrombosis Research*. 1994;76(1):71–78. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0049-3848\(94\)90208-9](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0049-3848(94)90208-9).
- 65) Gando S, Kameue T, Nanzaki S, Nakanishi Y. Cytokines, soluble thrombomodulin and disseminated intravascular coagulation in patients with systemic inflammatory response syndrome. *Thrombosis Research*. 1995;80(6):519–526. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0049-3848\(95\)00207-3](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0049-3848(95)00207-3).
- 66) Muller-Beghaus G. Pathophysiology and biochemical events in disseminated intravascular coagulation: dysregulation of procoagulant and anticoagulant pathway. *Semin Thromb Hemstas*. 1989;15:1815–1829.
- 67) Sarma JV, Ward PA. The complement system. *Cell and Tissue Research*. 2011;343(1):227–235. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00441-010-1034-0>.
- 68) Kaweckí C, Lenting PJ, Denis CV. Van Willibrand factor and inflammation. *Journal of Thrombosis & Haemostasis*.
- 69) Nakamura S, Nakamura I, Ma L, Vaughan DE, Fogo AB. Plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 expression is regulated by the angiotensin type 1 receptor in vivo. *Kidney International*. 2000;58(1):251–259. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1755.2000.00160.x>.
- 70) Kwann H. Coronavirus disease-2019: the role of fibrinolytic system from transmission to organ injury. *Semin Thrombosis and Hemostasis*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s0040-1709996>.
- 71) Skurk T, Lee YM, Hauner H. Angiotensin II and Its Metabolites Stimulate PAI-1 Protein Release From Human Adipocytes in Primary Culture. *Hypertension*. 2001;37(5):1336–1340. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.hyp.37.5.1336>.
- 72) Brown JN, Nadeau HJ, Vaughan ED. Selective Stimulation of Tissue-Type Plasminogen Activator (t-PA) In Vivo by Infusion of Bradykinin. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 1997;77(03):522–525. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1656000>.
- 73) Lippi G, South AM, Henry BM, Express A. Electrolyte imbalance in patients with severe coronavirus disease-2019. *Annals Clinical Biochemistry*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004563220922255>.
- 74) Yuan J, Jia R, Bao Y. Aldosterone Up-regulates Production of Plasminogen Activator Inhibitor-1 by Renal Mesangial Cells. *BMB Reports*. 2007;40(2):180–188. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5483/bmbrep.2007.40.2.180>.
- 75) Sawathiparnich P, Kumar S, Vaughan ED, Brown JN. Spironolactone Abolishes the Relationship between Aldosterone and Plasminogen Activator Inhibitor-1 in Humans. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2002;87(2):448–452. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1210/jcem.87.2.7980>.
- 76) Brown JN, Kim KS, Chen YQ, Blevins SL, Nadeau JH, Meranze GS, et al. Synergistic Effect of Adrenal Steroids and Angiotensin II on Plasminogen Activator Inhibitor-1 Production. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2000;85(1):336–344. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1210/jcem.85.1.6305>.
- 77) Minai K, Matsumoto T, Horie H, Ohira N, Takashima H, Yokohama H, et al. Bradykinin stimulates the release of tissue plasminogen activator in human coronary circulation: effects of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 2001;37(6):1565–1570. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097\(01\)01202-5](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097(01)01202-5).
- 78) Brown NJ, Baluta MM, Vintila MM. Plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 inhibition: another therapeutic option for cardiovascular protection. *Medica*. 2015;10(2):147–152.
- 79) Baudin B, Berard M, Carrier JL, Legrand Y, Drouet L. Vascular Origin Determines Angiotensin I-Converting Enzyme Expression in Endothelial Cells. *Endothelium*. 1997;5(1):73–84. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3109/10623329709044160>.
- 80) Taddei S, Versari D, Cipriano A, Ghiadoni L, Galetta F, Franzoni F, et al. Identification of a Cytochrome P450 2C9-Derived Endothelium-Derived Hyperpolarizing Factor in Essential Hypertensive Patients. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 2006;48(3):508–515. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2006.04.074>.
- 81) Taddei S, Ghiadoni L, Virdis A, Versari D, Salvetti A. Mechanisms of Endothelial Dysfunction: Clinical Significance and Preventive Non-Pharmacological Therapeutic Strategies. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*. 2003;9(29):2385–2402. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1381612033453866>.
- 82) Kossmann S, Hu H, Steven S, Schönfelder T, Fraccarollo D, Mikhed Y, et al. Inflammatory Monocytes Determine Endothelial Nitric-oxide Synthase Uncoupling and Nitro-oxidative Stress Induced by Angiotensin II. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2014;289(40):27540–27550. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1074/jbc.m114.604231>.
- 83) Ridker PM, Gaboury CL, Conlin PR, Seely EW, Williams GH, Vaughan DE. Stimulation of plasminogen activator inhibitor in vivo by infusion of angiotensin II. Evidence of a potential interaction between the renin-angiotensin system and fibrinolytic function. *Circulation*. 1993;87(6):1969–1973. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.87.6.1969>.
- 84) Tamarat R, Silvestre JS, Durie M, Levy BI. Angiotensin II Angiogenic Effect In Vivo Involves Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor- and Inflammation-Related Pathways. *Laboratory Investigation*. 2002;82(6):747–756. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1097/01.lab.0000017372.76297.eb>.
- 85) Ruiz-Ortega M, Lorenzo O, Ruperez M, Esteban V, Suzuki Y, Mazzano S, et al. Role of the renin angiotensin system in vascular disease: expanding the field. *Hypertension*. 2001;38:1382–1387.
- 86) Chen XL, Tummala EP, Olbrych TM, Alexander RW, Medford MR. Angiotensin II Induces Monocyte Chemoattractant Protein-1 Gene Expression in Rat Vascular Smooth Muscle Cells. *Circulation Research*. 1998;83(9):952–959. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.res.83.9.952>.
- 87) Ide N, Hirase T, Nishimoto-Hazuku A, Ikeda Y, Node K. Angiotensin II Increases Expression of IP-1 and the Renin-Angiotensin System in Endothelial Cells. *Hypertension Research*. 2008;31(6):1257–1267. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1291/hyres.31.1257>.
- 88) Akishita M, Nagai K, Xi H, Yu W, Sudoh N, Watanabe T, et al. Renin-Angiotensin System Modulates Oxidative Stress-Induced Endothelial Cell Apoptosis in Rats. *Hypertension*. 2005;45(6):1188–1193. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.hyp.0000165308.04703.f2>.
- 89) Tomasian D. Antioxidants and the bioactivity of endothelium-derived nitric oxide. *Cardiovascular Research*. 2000;47(3):426–435. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0008-6363\(00\)00103-6](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0008-6363(00)00103-6).
- 90) Luscher TF, Barton M. Biology of the endothelium. *Clinical Cardiology*. 1997;20:3–10.
- 91) Zhang H, Penninger MJ, Li Y, Zhong N, Slutsky SA. Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) as a SARS-CoV-2 receptor: molecular mechanisms and potential therapeutic target. *Intensive Care Medicine*. 2020;46(4):586–590. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00134-020-05985-9>.
- 92) Gupta N, Zhao YY, Evans CE. Stimulation of thrombosis by hypoxia. *Thromb Res*. 2019;181:77–83.
- 93) Xu Z, Shi L, Wang Y, Zhang J, Huang L, Zhang C. Pathological findings of COVID-19 associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Lancet Rep Med*. 2020;8:420–422.

- 94) Sardu C, Gambardella J, Morelli MB, Wang X, Marfella R, Santulli G. Hypertension, Thrombosis, Kidney Failure, and Diabetes: Is COVID-19 an Endothelial Disease? A Comprehensive Evaluation of Clinical and Basic Evidence. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2020;9(5):1417–1417. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jcm9051417>.
- 95) Dzau JV. Tissue Angiotensin and Pathobiology of Vascular Disease. *Hypertension*. 2001;37(4):1047–1052. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.hyp.37.4.1047>.
- 96) Griendling KK, Lassegue B, Murphy TZ, Alexander RW. Angiotensin-II receptor pharmacology. *Advance Pharmacology*. 1994;28:269–306.
- 97) Arenas AI, Xu Y, Lopez-Jaramillo P, Davidge TS. Angiotensin II-induced MMP-2 release from endothelial cells is mediated by TNF- α . *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology*. 2004;286(4):C779–C784. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.00398.2003>.
- 98) Su JB, Houel R, Holoire F, Barde F, Beverelli F, Sambin L, et al. Stimulation of bradykinin B(1) receptor induces vasodilation in conductance and resistance coronary vessels in conscious dog: comparison with B(2) receptor stimulation. *Circulation*. 2000;101:1848–1853.
- 99) Rahman MA, Murrow RJ, Ozkor AM, Kavtaradze N, Lin J, Staercke CD, et al. Endothelium-Derived Hyperpolarizing Factor Mediates Bradykinin-Stimulated Tissue Plasminogen Activator Release in Humans. *Journal of Vascular Research*. 2014;51(3):200–208. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000362666>.
- 100) Kwaan CH. Coronavirus Disease 2019: The Role of the Fibrinolytic System from Transmission to Organ Injury and Sequelae. *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*. 2020. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1709996>.
- 101) Ceconi C, Francolini G, Olivares A, Comini L, Bachetti T, Ferrari R. Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors have different selectivity for bradykinin binding sites of human somatic ACE. *European Journal of Pharmacology*. 2007;577(1-3):1–6. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2007.07.061>.
- 102) Lin L, Lu L, Cao W, Li T. Hypothesis for potential pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 infection—a review of immune changes in patients with viral pneumonia. *Emerging Microbes & Infections*. 2020;9(1):727–732. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1080/22221751.2020.1746199>.
- 103) Varga Z, Flammer AJ, Steiger P, Haberecker M, Andermatt R, Zinkernagel AS, et al. Endothelial cell infection and endotheliitis in COVID-19. *The Lancet*. 2020;395(10234):1417–1418. Available from: [https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30937-5](https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30937-5).
- 104) Sato R, Ishikane M, Kinoshita N, Suzuki T, Nakamoto T, Hayakawa K. A new challenge of unfractionated heparin anticoagulation treatment for moderate to severe COVID-19 in Japan. *Global Health & Medicine-Advance Publicaion*. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.35772/ghm-2020.01044>.
- 105) Mucha SR, Dugar S, McCrae K, Joseph D, Bartholomew J, Sacha GL, et al. Coagulopathy in COVID-19: Manifestations and management. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine*. 2020;87(8):461–468. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.87a.ccc024>.
- 106) Poterucha TJ, Libby P, Goldhaber SZ. More than an anticoagulant: Do heparins have direct anti-inflammatory effects? *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 2017;117(03):437–444. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1160/th16-08-0620>.
- 107) Lang J, Yang N, Deng J, Liu K, Yang P, Zhang G, et al. Inhibition of SARS Pseudovirus Cell Entry by Lactoferrin Binding to Heparan Sulfate Proteoglycans. *PLoS ONE*. 2011;6(8):e23710–e23710. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0023710>.
- 108) Mummery SR, Rider CC. Characterization of the Heparin-Binding Properties of IL-6. *The Journal of Immunology*. 2000;165(10):5671–5679. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.165.10.5671>.
- 109) Zhou F, Yu T, Du R, Fan G, Liu Y, Xiang J. Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: A retrospective cohort study. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10229):1054–1062. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30566-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30566-3).
- 110) Organization WH. Clinical management of severe acute respiratory infection when COVID-19 is suspected. 2020.